

BI-STABLE PIEZOELECTRIC COMPOSITE LAMINATE FOR ENERGY HARVESTING

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1. INTRODUCTION

Bi-stable composite laminates are recently investigated as an alternative method to achieve broadband vibration energy harvesting in a wide frequencies range, due to their complicated dynamics including nonlinear large amplitude oscillations between stable configurations [1, 2]. More than that, bi-stable composite laminates have several advantages, including design flexibility for multiple resonance tuning owing to their two-dimensional nature, and reduced complexity as no external magnets are required to achieve bi-stability [1, 3].

This work presents a bi-stable piezoelectric composite laminate (BPCL) based on bi-stable hybrid symmetric laminate (BHSL) and PZT transducer. It has several advantages: Firstly, it has two stable configurations which have the same curvatures with opposite signs, so it can be fixed at one end and works like a cantilevered harvester. Secondly, the double curved shape and uniform deformation of BHSL are beneficial to get homogeneous and large strains for the PZT transducers. Thirdly, the design flexibility is enhanced due to the hybrid design. The prototype is fabricated by experiments and a simple model is developed to estimate the output power under ideal continuous snap-through vibration pattern.

2. BI-STABLE PIEZOELECTRIC COMPOSITE LAMINATE

- Hybrid region:
 - $[90_2/Al/90_2]_T$
- Composite region:
 - $[0/90/0_2/90/0]_T$
- 32 pieces of PZTs
- PZTs are connected in parallel

3. EXPERIMENTS

- BPCL was fabricated by usual autoclave techniques and the PZT transducers were bonded on BHSL by epoxy resin included in prepregs during the curing process
- BPCL was actuated by shaker to trigger continuous snap-through vibration and generate power
- Excitation frequency was 8 Hz and amplitude was 5 mm

4. FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

- BPCL has a uniform voltage distribution

5. ANALYTICAL MODELLING AND RESULTS

- The assumption that BPCL transforms between two stable configurations ideally is supposed
- The strain variations of PZT transducers during the continuous snap-through process are the strain differences between two stable configurations
- Using a standard AC-DC circuit, the output power of BPCL under ideal continuous snap-through vibration pattern is deduced as below

$$D_3 = d_{31} \frac{(\varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2)}{S_{11} + S_{12}} + \varepsilon_{33} E_3 \quad \frac{V_{DC}}{R} \frac{T}{2} = \int_t^{t+T} Idt = Q_B - Q_A \quad Q_B - Q_A = A \left(\frac{d_{31} (\Delta\varepsilon_1 + \Delta\varepsilon_2)}{S_{11} + S_{12}} - 2 \frac{V_{DC}}{t} \varepsilon_{33} \right) \quad P = \frac{R \left(Ad_{31} \frac{(\Delta\varepsilon_1 + \Delta\varepsilon_2)}{S_{11} + S_{12}} \right)^2}{\left(2\varepsilon_{33} AR \frac{1}{t} + \frac{T}{2} \right)^2}$$

Maximum Power: 44.4 mW

6. CONCLUSIONS

- The bi-stable piezoelectric composite laminate can output higher power and power density at a relatively lower frequency owing to its characteristics of the uniform strains of PZT transducers.
- Improving continuous snap-through vibration frequency is an effective way to increase output power

REFERENCES

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3. Betts, D. N., Kim, H. A., Bowen, C. R., and Inman, D. J., *International Society for Optics and Photonics*, 2012.